

ALKYLATION OF KETONES

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A suitable method for alkylation of ketones is to prepare first oxymethylene compound of the ketone (2-formyl ketone). By treating sodium derivative of the 2-formyl ketone with the alkyl halide, 2-formyl 2-alkyl ketone is formed which on ketonic hydrolysis yields 2-alkyl ketone. The process is illustrated by the synthesis of 2-ethylcyclohexanone from cyclohexanone.

If a 1:3-diketone —CO—CH—CO— in the form of its sodium enolate —C=C—CO— is treated with an alkyl halide, alkylation takes place in 2-position. A simple ketone —CO—CH— should similarly be capable of being alkylated in 2-position if its sodium

enolate —C=C— could be obtained. Generally, by the action of sodium on a ketone some amount of its sodium enolate is formed, but simultaneously sodium compounds of secondary reaction products are also formed. For instance, by the action of sodium on methylethyl ketone, not only the sodium enolate of the ketone (I) but also sodium compound of 3:4-dimethylhexane-diol-3:4 (II) is produced, obviously by reduction of the ketone by hydrogen evolved in the formation of sodium enolate (I) (Braun, *Monats*, 1906, 27, 804).

By the action of alkyl halides on sodium compounds formed from cyclohexanone, menthone, carvone and methylethyl ketone, we failed to obtain any appreciable amount of the corresponding 2-alkyl ketones.

Beckmann (*J. prakt. Chem*, 1897 ii, 55, 35) describes that the so-called 'sodium camphor', obtained by the action of sodium on camphor, dissolved in ether, contains also sodium borneol and sodium isoborneol. By keeping *l*-camphor dissolved in dry ether in contact with sodium dust at room temperature, we found that the sodium practically went into solution. On adding bromine to the 'sodium camphor', thus formed, we obtained an excellent yield of 2-bromo-*l*-camphor. The 'sodium camphor', therefore consisted mostly of the sodium enolate of camphor, and as expected, when it was treated with *n*-butyl bromide it gave us 2-*n*-butyl-*l* camphor (III).

An indirect formation of a 2-alkyl ketone through 2-chloro-ketone has been shown by Tiffeneau and Tchoubar (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 941). These authors have shown that when magnesiummethyl iodide is added at room temperature to 2-chlorocyclohexanone, the reaction takes place at the keto group rather than at the chlorine of the ketone, and organo-magnesium derivative (IV) is formed, from which by decomposition with water 2-chloro-1-methylcyclohexanol (V) is obtained. If, however, (IV) is boiled in ether, magnesium halide separates, the methyl group migrates to 2-position, and 2-methylcyclohexanone (VI) is finally obtained.

Working with 2-bromo-1-camphor we found that when magnesiummethyl iodide was added to its ethereal solution at ice temperature, magnesium halide began to separate almost immediately and on completion of separation we obtained 2-ethyl-1-camphor (VII) from the filtrate. In this case, at any rate, the alkylation of ketone does not seem to be indirect, but direct in 2-position.

As, however, 2-chloro-ketones cannot be obtained easily, this method is not of general utility for preparing 2-alkyl ketones.

A method which we have found reliable and convenient for obtaining 2-alkyl ketones is through 2-formyl ketones (oxymethylene ketones). The latter are obtained by treating ketones with ethyl formate and sodium. The preparation of 2-ethylcyclohexanone, one of the 2-alkylated ketones we have prepared, will illustrate the process.

2-Formylcyclohexanone (oxymethylene cyclohexanone) (VIII), prepared from cyclohexanone and ethyl formate, was treated with sodium ethylate, and the sodium derivative of the 1:3-dicarbonyl compound reacted with ethyl iodide to give 2-formyl-2-ethylcyclohexanone (IX). By ketonic hydrolysis of (IX) the formyl group was removed and 2-ethylcyclohexanone (X) was obtained.

Paranjpye, Bhide and Nargund prepared 2-formyl-2-methylcyclohexanone in crude form which they could not purify by distillation (*Nature*, 1944, 153, 141). They reported that their crude product was optically active having specific rotation $[\alpha]_D = -26.22^\circ$. Such an asymmetric synthesis being highly improbable the process of methylation of 2-formylcyclohexanone was examined by O'Golman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1041) and by Cornforth, Cornforth and Dewar (*Nature*, 1944, 153, 317). In none of these experiments was the methylation product found to be optically active. The higher homologue, 2-formyl-2-ethylcyclohexanone (IX) in our case, was found to be completely inactive, as expected.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium l-camphor and 2-Bromo-l-camphor.—Sodium dust, prepared by melting 2.3 g. (1 atom) of sodium under boiling xylene and vigorous shaking, was covered by dry ether and kept cool. A solution of *l*-camphor (15.2 g., 1 mol.) in dry ether was then gradually added. The mixture was allowed to remain at room temperature for 6 days when most of the sodium dissolved as 'sodium camphor', a small amount of brown mass remaining outside.

To the 'sodium camphor', kept at 0° , was added gradually a solution of bromine (16-g.) in dry carbon tetrachloride. Bromine was rapidly absorbed and sodium bromide separating was removed by filtration. The filtrate on being freed from slight excess of bromine by alkali was washed and dried and the solvent removed. From the residue unchanged camphor was removed by distilling up to 215° . The solid residue obtained on cooling was crystallised from dilute alcohol in plates, m. p. 76° , yield 16 g. (70% of theory). It was identified as *l*-bromocamphor from its melting point and bromine content.

2-n-Butyl-l-camphor (III).—To 'sodium camphor', prepared as described above, was added *n*-butyl bromide (13.7 g., 1 mol.). The mixture was gently refluxed on a water-bath for 7 hours when the reaction became nearly neutral and sodium bromide separated. On cooling, the mixture was made slightly acid, the ether layer was washed and dried and the solvent removed. On distilling the remaining liquid 4.5 g. passed between 50° and 90° at 90 mm. The remainder solidified in the distilling flask on cooling. The solid freed from adhering liquid weighed 7 g. and crystallised from dilute alcohol in feathery needles, m. p. 188° (*l*-camphor, m. p. 175°): $[\alpha]_D$ in alcohol = -32.1° . [Found: C, 80.6; H, 10.8. $C_{14}H_{24}O$ (butyl camphor) requires C, 80.8; H, 11.5 per cent. $C_{10}H_{18}O$ (camphor) requires C, 78.9; H, 10.5 per cent.]. 2-*n*-Butyl-*l*-camphor forms a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 169° .

2-Ethyl-l-camphor (VII).—Grignard reagent (prepared from Mg, 1.2 g. and ethyl iodide in dry ether) was gradually added to a cooled solution of 9.2 g. of 2-bromo-*l*-camphor in dry ether. The whole was allowed to remain at ice temperature over-

night. Greyish white magnesium halide separated. The reaction was completed by warming for a few minutes. The product was poured into dilute hydrochloric acid, the ether layer was washed and dried and the solvent removed. A white solid free from bromine was left. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 148° ; $[\alpha]_D = -128.7^{\circ}$ in alcohol. (Found: C, 79.2; H, 10.8. $C_{14}H_{20}O$ requires C, 80.0; H, 11.0 per cent). It forms a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 188° .

2-Ethyl-*d*-camphor was prepared by Boubigny (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1886, II, 409) by treating sodium *d*-camphor with ethyl iodide in toluene at 60° , and is described as a liquid, b. p. 226° - 231° . Since the corresponding *l*-stereoisomer (di-*z*-stereoisomere of the above) prepared by us was a solid, it became necessary to confirm its isomerism with the above by preparing it by Baubigny's method using *l*-camphor instead of *d*-camphor. The product obtained was a mixture of *l*-camphor and 2-ethyl-*l*-camphor. Separation was effected by repeated crystallisation followed by sublimation, the former subliming more readily than the latter. 2-Ethyl-*l*-camphor, thus obtained, was finally purified by crystallisation, m. p. 148° and it formed a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 188° . Thus, the 2-ethyl-*l*-camphor, prepared from sodium *l*-camphor and ethyl iodide, was found to be identical with the product obtained from *l*-bromocamphor and magnesium ethyl iodide. 2-Methylation of *d*-camphor through sodium *d*-camphor was effected with great difficulty by Haller (*Compt. rend.*, 1809, 148, 1645), the reaction product being always a mixture of *d*-camphor and methylated *d*-camphor.

2-Formyl-2-ethylcyclohexanone (IX) from Formylcyclohexanone (VIII).—To sodium ethylate, prepared from sodium (1 g.) and absolute alcohol (35 c.c.), formylcyclohexanone (6 g.) was gradually added under cooling, and then ethyl iodide (6.9 g.) was added. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 hours when it gave nearly neutral reaction. On removing excess of alcohol and acidifying, a deep green liquid resulted which was extracted with carbon tetrachloride. After washing, drying and removing the solvent the remaining liquid distilled at 81° - $84^{\circ}/3\text{mm.}$, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 9.5. $C_8H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 70.1; H, 9.1 per cent). The compound gives a blue colour with ferric chloride and forms a semicarbazone, m. p. 145° (semicarbazone of 2-formylcyclohexanone, m. p. 231°).

Ketonic Hydrolysis of 2-Formyl-2-ethylcyclohexanone: Formation of 2-Ethylcyclohexanone (X).—Caustic potash (15 c.c., 10%) was added to 2-formyl-2-ethylcyclohexanone in a small flask, and the mixture was gently refluxed on a sand-bath for 5 hours when a reddish oily layer was seen floating over aqueous alkali. This was extracted with ether, the solvent washed, dried and removed. The residual liquid distilled at $90^{\circ}/65\text{ mm.}$

2-Ethylcyclohexanone was prepared by Leser (*Compt. rend.*, 1806, 141, 1033) by the action of hot alkali on 1-ethyl-1-acetylcyclohexanone and is described as liquid, b. p. $65^{\circ}/10\text{ mm.}$ (semicarbazone, m. p. 157°) (Found: C, 75.9; H, 11.4. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires C, 76.2; H, 11.1 per cent).

2-Ethylcyclohexanone is a colorless liquid with camphor-like odour. It forms a semicarbazone, m. p. 155° .